

Be Little, Do Not Belittle

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Abstract

Belittling others and validating oneself as righteous is the way of the world. The Old and the New Testament has various examples of people belittling the other to show one's own superiority. Cain belittles Able, Joseph is belittled by his brothers, Eliab belittles David, Job is belittled by his friends and the elder son belittles his father and brother in the story of the Prodigal Son. All these examples of belittling are in reverse relation to the example of Jesus' life. Jesus allows himself to be belittled through his incarnation, the incident of the washing of the feet as well as through his Passion and Death. His way is to 'be little' for the other so that the others may be exalted. Thus, the concept of 'being little' in God's kingdom is an invitation to approach God with childlike faith, humility, and a readiness to serve others.

Introduction

Belittling, or making someone feel small or insignificant, is a recurring motif in the Bible. Many personalities are made fun of, criticised, insulted, accused, or rejected by others. Power imbalances, societal hierarchies, or conflicts between individuals or groups are frequently reflected in this treatment. Such an attitude is not merely condemned in the bible rather is abhorred. According to Dr. Brené Brown's studies, belittling and criticising others can have a comparable effect on their sense of value. In her book '*Rising Strong*,' she writes, "When we judge or criticize another person, it says nothing about that person; it merely says something about our own need to be critical" (Brown, 2015, 61). Speech speaks about the speaker. There are many characters, within the bible, who belittle others so as to display their worth as superior to the others. On the other hand, it is Jesus who invites his disciples to be humble, which is clearly implied in his action of washing the feet of his disciples (Jn 13:2-17) as well as his invitation to be childlike (Matt 18:1-3). 'Being little' is not merely an act but a process, which can be observed in and through the life of Jesus.

Cain Belittles Abel

A comparative analysis between the behavioural pattern between Cain and Abel denotes a hate relationship between the two brothers. Cain downplayed Abel's value and importance when God enquired about Abel. Cain responded by asking rhetorically, "Am I my brother's keeper?" (Gen 4:9). This response can be interpreted as an attempt to minimise or invalidate Abel's life. Certain characteristics that determine the personhood of Cain are: jealousy, resentfulness, anger, envious and unfaithfulness. On the other hand, the characteristics Abel as a person displayed are: faithful, obedient, righteous, devout and victimized. Abel in his righteousness remained faithful to Yahweh. He gave the best produce to God which merged with his spirit of devotion and respect made it favourable in God's sight. He chose to live a righteous life even in the face of persecution and violence. 'Belittling' others is to downplay the other but 'Being Little' is to follow a path of humbleness and faithfulness to God.

Joseph Belittled by His Brothers

The brothers of Joseph were jealous of him and in their resentment and animosity towards Joseph they attempted to murder him and eventually sell him into slavery (Gen 37:23-28). Their words of belittlement about Joseph were expressed in their lie which they narrated to their father Jacob (Gen 37:31-33). They do not term Joseph as 'our brother' rather as 'your son' (Gen 37:32) when they bring the coat dipped in animal blood to Jacob. This shows their distancing from Joseph. Joseph's brothers were deceptive, resentful, jealous and angry. Joseph, on the other hand, is portrayed as compassionate and generous. Joseph was victimized by his own brothers. He was belittled for being the favourite of their father. He was sold into slavery like an object. A despicable act. In spite of all this Joseph remained faithful to Yahweh at Potiphar's house (Gen 39:7-20), he forgave his brothers and reconciled with them (Gen 50:15-21). He epitomizes forgiveness and mercy as he reaches out to them in their need. Thus, greatness is not in being the victimizer rather in rising to the occasion and forgiving others. Being Little is all about humbling oneself, just like Joseph, who humbled himself even after being a very important person in the Egyptian kingdom.

Eliab Belittles David

The narrative of David and Goliath is one of the most famous examples of belittling in the Bible (1 Sam 17). Goliath, the colossal Philistine warrior, challenged the Israelite army to send a champion to face him in single battle. He belittled the Israelites who, looking at his stature, were afraid of him and wouldn't want to face

him. David, a little shepherd boy, offered to fight Goliath but was mocked by his older brother Eliab, who accused him of arrogance and folly (1 Sam 17:28). Eliab, being the firstborn of Jesse, was the heir of the divine promise. As Von Rad states, “the privilege of the first-born was absolutely uncontested in the ancient Orient,” (Von Rad, 1973, p. 416) and this might have been the cause of an ill feeling between David and Eliab. Samuel assumed that Eliab, being the first born, would be selected as King (1 Sam 16:6) but Yahweh selected David, who was the youngest (1 Sam 16:13). About Eliab, Yahweh stated that he does not judge based on outward appearance rather by what is in the heart (1 Sam 16:7). The true nature of Eliab emerged only when he mocked David in 1 Sam 17:28 and called David a spoiled brat. 1 Sam 16:1-13 doesn’t state any comment by his brothers upon David’s selection and anointing, it is only in 1 Sam 17:28 that the grudge of Eliab emerged. He belittled David for being a shepherd boy and not a soldier. David, on the contrary, was seen as the chosen one (1 Sam 16:13), an obedient son (1 Sam 17:20), a mighty warrior (1 Sam 17:51). In spite of being belittled by others, he was exalted by Yahweh for his faithfulness and dependence on him. David’s courage, humility, faith, and perseverance helped him to contribute in a way that no other could.

Job Belittled by His Friends

Job’s friends come to comfort him but end up accusing him of deserving his suffering because of his supposed wrongdoing. For example, Eliphaz says to Job, “Is not your wickedness great? There is no end to your iniquities” (Job 22:5). Bildad similarly suggested that Job’s children may have sinned and thus deserved their deaths (Job 8:3). Zophar insisted that Job must have done something to deserve his suffering (Job 11:6). They belittled Job for his miserable condition and hold him responsible for it. Job’s friends believed they understood the cause of Job’s suffering, and their attempts to explain it were driven by a desire to make sense of an apparent unfair circumstance. The friends unsympathetically accused him of being arrogant and foolish. Though having suffered immense loss, Job was steadfast in his belief in God’s justice and goodness. In the end, Job was restored of his fortunes. The restoration of his fortunes is seen as a reward for his steadfastness and a testament to God’s ultimate justice and goodness.

Elder Son Belittles the Younger One

The story of the Prodigal son (Lk 15:11-32) is well known to all. The elder son’s statement, “But when this son of yours who has squandered your property with prostitutes comes home, you kill the fattened calf for him!” (Lk 15:30) belittles not

just the younger brother but the father himself. He did not call the younger son as ‘my brother’ rather he distanced himself from him by calling him ‘your son.’ Moreover, he did not see the repentant heart of the younger brother nor the loving attitude of the father rather he focused on their faults. He upheld his attitude as being faithful and downplayed the attitude of the father of unconditionally loving the younger son. The elder son felt that he had been overlooked and unappreciated, and his bitterness led him to belittle his brother and father. The parable teaches that Being Little makes one great. The father by accepting his repentant son humbles himself and thus is an example for humility and love. Anger, bitterness, and self-righteous behaviour can hinder in experiencing God’s love.

Being Little

The term ‘little’ is an adjective. The Hebrew term ‘קטן’ (qaton - little) signifies size of an object or even ‘insignificant’ or ‘weak.’ In Greek, the term used is ‘μικρός’ (mikros - little) which means small in relation to humility and a dependent character. Jesus often used the term ‘little ones’ or ‘the least of these’ to signify that however little someone may be they have great significance in the eyes of God. Jesus established the small-great reversal through the parable of the Mustard Seed (Mt 13:31-32). Through Mt 18:1-4, Jesus encouraged his listeners to be like little children, thus taking upon themselves lowliness and humility in order to be part of the Kingdom of God. In Lk 12:32 Jesus has said, “Do not be afraid, little flock, for your Father has been pleased to give you the kingdom.” This statement highlights Jesus’ focus on small and humble people who are faithful to God. There are three key incidents in Jesus’ life that signify that ‘being little’ is the path to the Kingdom. The Incarnation, the washing of the feet, and finally, the passion and death of Jesus, signify the importance of being little.

The Incarnation: Jesus’ earthly life began by being little. There was no decent place for his birth (Lk 2:7), he was brought up in a small, insignificant town of Nazareth (Mt. 2:23), he was a carpenter’s son (Mk 6:3), associated with sinners (Mk 2:13-17) and moreover, he was called as an itinerant wanderer. Jesus’ humble beginnings in Bethlehem’s stable and upbringing in a tiny town emphasised his kinship with the poor and lowly. The glorious one became small, humble and reversed the idea that big and large was important rather he emphasized on the fact that Being Little and small was significant.

Washing of the Feet: Jesus’ servant attitude is a pure example of how he considered the least as the most important ones. In the ancient near east, the task of washing the feet was typically of a low-ranking servant (Eerdmans, 2011, 594), an insignificant job, not to be done by a person of high social status. What Jesus

emphasized through the act of washing of the feet is that ‘being little’ is the path that one should follow and not the path of ‘belittling others.’ Being Little means being humble, hospitable, respectful, and service-oriented. Being little is the path to enter the Kingdom.

Passion and Death: Jesus’ passion and death as described by John the evangelist (Jn 18-19) significantly places before us a variety of nuances that speak of Jesus being made the lowest among all. The officer, who slapped Jesus and retorted “Is this how you answer the high priest?” (Jn 18:22), belittles Jesus and upholds the high priest office. The soldiers mocked Jesus when they said, “Hail King of the Jews” (Jn 19:3). They meant to ridicule him in a sarcastic way as they did not believe him to be the King. Pilate expressed his authority and his power over Jesus by saying, “Do you not know that I have power to release you, and power to crucify you? (Jn 19:10) which showed the greatness of Pilate and the helplessness of Jesus. It is a statement of belittlement of Jesus and the might of the Romans. The death penalty of Jesus was the final belittlement of Jesus. The Saviour of the world was hanging on the cross like a criminal. The sinless one was now displayed to be the sinful one, who had no demeanour nor value. The purpose of the crucifixion was to make the person feel so little that his life did not matter. And from this belittlement of Jesus emerges the true nature of God. God through this belittlement paves a pathway for humanity to enter the Kingdom. Being little is the pathway to being great.

Conclusion

The world at large promotes a person to be someone. It makes the ‘I’ the centre of the universe. It encourages one to have self-worth, which emphasises one’s own value and worthiness as an individual at the cost of others. The belittling of the other makes way for oneself to be forthright and powerful. This is contradictory to the path which Jesus suggested. Jesus promoted the idea that one needs to be little on purpose. As Dr Shailendra states, “Jesus was portraying himself as the God of little things on the streets of Israel. He was interested in the lost and the least. He was God in search of the least” (Shailendra, 2015, 58-59).

Being Little includes being humble, innocent, and having childlike trust in God. One needs to know that the other too is a child of God and act accordingly. Self-worth is great if it includes faith and humility and not pride and selfishness. It is great if the other is at the centre of life and the ‘I’ is seen in BEiNG LiTTLE. Thus, the concept of Being Little in God’s kingdom is an invitation to approach God with childlike faith, humility, and a readiness to serve others. This entails acknowledging our own limitations and inadequacies and relying on God’s strength

and grace to lead us along the way. By accepting these characteristics, we can feel a stronger connection to God and grow in our faith and relationship with Him. Let us move from belittling other to Being Little. So, Be Little rather than belittling someone.

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